

THE REACTION BETWEEN AQUEOUS IODINE AND SODIUM FORMATE.

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The reaction between aqueous iodine and sodium formate has been studied in the dark and the effect of various salts, such as KCl, NaCl, NH₄Cl, K₂SO₄, NaNO₃ and NH₄I investigated. It is observed that effect of the three chlorides is similar: velocity constant at first increases with the concentration of chlorides and then falls. It seems that though Cl⁻ ions act as positive catalyst, K⁺, Na⁺ and NH₄⁺ ions retard the reaction, the order being NH₄⁺ > Na⁺ > K⁺. It also appears that NaCl, KCl and NH₄Cl molecules likewise retard the reaction. The effect of iodide ion in NH₄I is comparable to that in KI. Temperature coefficient of the reaction in aqueous iodine is less than in presence of KI. The relation between intensity and velocity for this reaction in presence and absence of KI and other salts has been investigated and in all cases the relationship was found to be less than direct.

The dark reaction between sodium formate and iodine dissolved in potassium iodide was studied by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707) and by Doosag and Bhagwat (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 331; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 216, 241). No work seems to have been done using aqueous iodine free from potassium iodide. In this paper the reaction between aqueous iodine and sodium formate has been investigated and the effect of various salts on this reaction is recorded.

TABLE I.

Dark reaction in absence of potassium iodide.

Conc. of I₂ = 0.001207N. Conc. of HCOONa = 0.48 g. per litre. 50 C.c. of each solution were mixed together and various quantities of the solid salt dissolved in it.

Temp.	Salt.	Amount.	K ₁ .	Temp.	Salt.	Amount.	K ₁ .	
30.5°	KCl	0	0.00582	30.5°	NaNO ₃	0	0.0058	
		0.5	0.00630			0.9471	0.0050	
		1.0	0.00650			1.6576	0.0046	
		2.0	0.00493			2.16	0.0048	
	NaCl	0	0.00580		KNO ₃	0	0.0058	
		0.5	0.00637			0.5	0.0052	
		1.0	0.00514			1.1275	0.0051	
	NH ₄ Cl	0	0.0058			2.0	0.0049	
		0.3246	0.0064					
		0.9965	0.0046					
		2.3631	0.0028					
	K ₂ SO ₄	0	0.0058	24.°	Conc. of I ₂ = 0.00113N. Conc. of HCOONa = 0.96 g. per litre.	NH ₄ I	0	0.00400
		1.2320	0.0060				0.8280	0.000234
		2.0144	0.0056					

REACTION BETWEEN AQUEOUS IODINE AND SODIUM FORMATE 305

The results clearly show that the effect of the three chlorides is similar. The velocity coefficient in all cases passes through a maximum, showing that though Cl^- ion acts as positive catalyst, the cations actually retard the reaction, the order being $\text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$. Moreover, the decrease in the velocity coefficient with the increased concentration of the chlorides shows that these molecules also retard the reaction, since the concentration of these molecules increases with the increased concentration of the salt with consequent decrease in the degree of dissociation.

K_2SO_4 , KNO_3 , and NaNO_3 retard the reaction, NaNO_3 showing the maximum effect, thus confirming the view that Na^+ ion has a greater retarding effect than K^+ ions on this reaction.

NH_4I like KI retards the reaction and when their results are expressed in terms of the concentration of iodide ion, retardation becomes proportional to it.

The first addition of KI causes remarkable fall in the velocity coefficient, but subsequent fall is proportional to the concentration of KI , as is evident from Table II.

TABLE II.

Conc. of $\text{HCOONa} = 5.2612$ g. per litre. $\text{I}_2 = 0.00123\text{N}$. Temp. = 30° .

Amount of KI .	K_1 .	Ratio of K_1 .	Ratio of $\frac{1}{K_1}$.
0	0.00465	$\frac{1.039}{0.335} = 3$	$\frac{0.00351}{0.00123} = 2.9$
0.335	0.00351	$\frac{2.15}{1.039} = 2.1$	$\frac{0.00123}{0.000562} = 2.1$
1.039	0.00123		
2.15	0.000562	$\frac{2.15}{0.335} = 6.3$	$\frac{0.00351}{0.000562} = 6.1$

The temperature coefficient of this reaction in presence of KI is recorded in a previous paper (*loc. cit.*) and K_{26}/K_{21} has the value of 2.1. In absence of KI the temperature coefficient falls and

$$K_{24}/K_{29} = \frac{0.0140}{0.0091} = 1.53, \text{ whence } K_{26}/K_{21} = 1.54$$

Decrease in the temperature coefficient in absence of KI is in accordance with our explanation that the acceleration of a reaction depends upon its initial velocity. Under same conditions, the velocity of reaction is greater in absence of KI than in its presence and hence the acceleration in absence of KI is smaller. The temperature coefficient is therefore less in aqueous iodine than in iodine dissolved in KI . Acceleration depends on the number of inactive molecules activated and always the same fraction of inactive molecules is activated according to Maxwell's rule for the

same change of temperature. Hence when initial velocity is correspondingly higher, the number of inactive molecules is smaller and acceleration due to temperature is therefore also smaller.

The photochemical reaction between sodium formate and iodine in presence of a definite quantity of potassium iodide was first investigated by Mukherji and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 850) but the reaction between aqueous iodine and sodium formate in light remained uninvestigated. The relation between intensity and velocity for this reaction was studied by Dhar and Bhattacharya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 475) but they did not avoid the presence of potassium iodide. They showed that the relation between intensity and velocity may be direct, less than direct or greater than direct depending on the amount of photochemical acceleration over the reaction.

In a previous paper (Bhagwat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 443), it has been shown that photochemical acceleration is a function of inactive molecules existing in the reacting system at the time of activation by light and that true photochemical reactions must always show a relationship which is less than direct and can never show a relationship greater than unity. The results obtained in the present investigation confirm the above conclusion (*cf.* Bhagwat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 649) and other numerous reactions: it is also confirmed in the present reaction between sodium formate and aqueous iodine with and without the addition of various salts. Results are shown in the following tables.

TABLE III.

Reaction in absence of potassium iodide.

Conc. of $I_2 = 0.00123N$. Conc. of $HCOONa = 0.9252$ g. per litre. In all cases 2g. of the salt are added to 100 c.c. of the mixture.

Temp.	Salt.	Dark K_1	Distance from source	True K_1 in light.	Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of velocities.
28°	Nil	0.0095	0.5 metre	0.0035	4	$\frac{0.0035}{0.0022} = 1.6$
			1	0.0022	—	—
			2	0.0010	16	$\frac{0.0031}{0.0010} = 3.5$
28°	KBr	0.0047	0.5	0.0031	9	$\frac{0.0031}{0.0008} = 3.9$
			1.5	0.0008	—	—
26°	KCl	0.00366	0.5	0.00161	4	$\frac{0.00161}{0.00098} = 1.6$
			1	0.00098	—	—
			2	0.00054	16	$\frac{0.00161}{0.00054} = 3.0$
25.2°	NH_4Cl	0.0034	2	0.00020	4	$\frac{0.00040}{0.00020} = 2$
			1	0.00040	—	—

TABLE IV.

Reaction in presence of potassium iodide.

Conc. of $I_2 = N/21.55$. Conc. of $KI = 51.7181$ g. per litre. Conc. of $HCOONa = 32$ g. per litre. In all cases 2 g. of the salt are added to 100 c.c. of the mixture.

Temp.	Salt.	Dark K_1 .	Distance from source.	True K_1 in light.	Ratio of intensities.	Ratio of velocities.
24°	Nil	0.0055	1 metre	0.00080	4	$\frac{0.00080}{0.00040} = 2$
			2	0.00040	—	—
25°	KBr	0.0061	0.5	0.00060	4	$\frac{0.00060}{0.00035} = 1.75$
			1	0.00035	—	—
			2	0.00020	16	$\frac{0.00060}{0.00020} = 3$
24°	NaBr	0.0059	0.5	0.00085	4	$\frac{0.00085}{0.00060} = 1.41$
			1	0.00060	—	—
			2	0.00030	16	$\frac{0.00085}{0.00030} = 2.85$
26°	NaI	0.00132	1	0.00030	—	$\frac{0.00030}{0.00016} = 1.9$
			2	0.00016	—	—
24.2°	NH_4I	0.00132	1	0.00013	4	$\frac{0.00013}{0.00007} = 1.9$
			2	0.00007	—	—

All these results point out that even in presence of potassium iodide and other salts, when the reaction is highly retarded, the relation between intensity and velocity never exceeds unity but it always remains appreciably lower.